

Water-tightness Airborne Detection Implementation

Technology and Application

WADI water leak detection surveillance service consists in the application of optical remote sensing on manned and unmanned aerial platforms. This innovative and cost-effective technology will be tested on two pilot sites located in the Provence region (France) and in Alqueva (Portugal).

WADI's innovative optical remote sensing concept integrates **hyper-spectral imaging, multi-spectral images** and **thermographic infrared (TIR) cameras**.

This will allow to:

- Detect water precisely thanks to the synergetic use of TIR and multispectral images combined with the triangle/trapezoid method for soil moisture evaluation
- Measure soil humidity through optimised wavelengths detection (visible, near infrared and long infrared domain)
- Implement WADI's service on a wide range of water transmission infrastructures such as dams, reservoirs, pressurised and gravity mains etc.

The solution developed by the WADI project will be applied on **two complementary aerial platforms**, i.e. **manned and unmanned**, typically used for distinctive purposes. The manned aircraft is used in long-distance and important infrastructure monitoring, whereas the unmanned platform is used for surveying branched water networks with short conduits and areas with difficult access or requiring closer monitoring upon earlier detection of anomalies during aircraft missions.

WADI's service will be tested in an **operational environment** in two pilot sites, different for infrastructure type and age, water uses, accessibility, soil plant cover type etc. This variety of conditions will provide an opportunity to demonstrate the full potential of WADI technique in real settings.

PILOT SITES:

Provence Region, France – Managed by Société Canal de Provence

Société Canal de Provence (SCP) operates and maintains a large scale hydraulic infrastructure totalling 5,500 km of canals, galleries and pipes over a territory of 31,400 square kilometers. Its infrastructure delivers water for cities, industries and irrigation.

Alqueva, Portugal – Managed by EDIA

The general system consists of 69 dams, reservoirs and weirs, 380 km of primary network, 1,620 km of pipes on the secondary network, 47 pumping stations, five mini-hydroelectric plants and a photovoltaic plant.

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